

Modulation in classical salt analysis technique to achieve nano-molar detection of heavy metal ions[†]

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Abstract : Due to unregulated use of heavy metal ions in industrial, its concentration in ground water increasing up to alarming level. To avoid the harmful effect on health, the receptors are required for their removal and detection in water. To achieve this we have develop a salen based receptor, conjugated with imidazolium cation. Here bromide ion act as counter ion as well as provide selectivity for heavy metal ion. The present approach is better than previously reported methods in various aspects such as low detection limit, working in aqueous medium, turn on fluorescent response and selectivity for heavy metal ions over other competing ions. The stoichiometry of binding was established using Job's plot which was found to be 1 : 1. Upon complexation with metal ion, emission intensity of receptor increases 8-fold due to cancelation of PET mechanism.

Keywords : PET, ionic liquids, organic cation, heavy metal ion.

Introduction

Development of sensitive molecular probes for toxic metal ions is gaining tremendous interest due to their unregulated use in industry¹⁻⁴. Especially, in developing countries disposal of industrial waste is a big problem^{5,6}. Therefore simple low cost receptors that can selectively bind with toxic metal ions are needed. Although another analytical techniques are available for elemental analysis such as atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS), ion chromatography (IC), induced couple plasma (ICP) and electrochemical methods etc.⁷⁻⁹. These technique have some limitation as it need extensive calibrations before recording the readings. The fluorescent/chromogenic receptors has many advantage over these classic technique; i.e. naked eye detection, low detection limit and high specificity^{1,10-14}. Many fluorescent and chromogenic probes are reported that are based on organic conjugated receptors and metal complex based sensors¹⁵⁻¹⁷. The major problems with organic receptors are their insolubility in aqueous medium, whereas in case of metal complexes; stability of complex and interference of another ionic

species are major issue^{18,19}. Aqueous solubility can be achieved by making organic nanoparticles, self-assembled aggregates, formation of organic inorganic nano hybrids or conjugating probe with cationic group²⁰⁻²⁴. Among these organic cationic receptors are promising candidates for selective detection of analyte^{25,26}. In last few years highly selective sensing of analytes were achieved in purely aqueous medium using ionic liquids²⁷⁻²⁹. Resently Yang *et al.* has developed imidazolium cation coupled fluorescent receptor for cell image of iron. They have used ionic interaction of imidazolium cation with adenosine triphosphate to form fluorescent organic nanoparticles which selectively loss their emission upon interaction with iron³⁰.

Structure of receptor N1.

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Previously our group has reported imidazolium cation based receptor for recognitions of amino acids, anions and biomolecules³¹⁻³³. In continuation of our previous work, we have prepared a salen based receptor conjugated with imidazolium ionic liquid. Here salen moiety will bind selectively with metal ion and counter ion (bromide) will also provide addition sensitivity and selectivity. As we know that in classical salt analysis experiments, first group elements detected by addition of hydrochloric acid. The chloride salt of metal ions were separated out due to high binding affinity of chloride with Ag^I, Pb^{II} and Hg^{II}. However it can detect these analyte only at high concentration (at least 10 mM). Therefore this technique cannot be used for environment analysis. Because in real samples; the concentration of metal ions are in parts per million. To achieve nano-molar detection of these analytes we prepared bromide salt of imidazolium ionic liquid. Keep this in mind that bromide will interact strongly with first group elements and also favor covalent interaction with salen moiety. Initially receptor **N1** was non fluorescent, due to presence of free lone pair on nitrogen and oxygen which causes fluorescence quenching by photo-induced electron transfer. However upon interacting with metal ions lone pair will transfer on metal ion and cause cancellation of PET mechanism³⁴⁻³⁶. Therefore present work is better than previous reported literature in various aspects such as sensing in aqueous medium, low detection limit and it can also be applicable for real sample analysis.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization :

The receptor **N1** was synthesized by condensation reaction between imidazolium coupled aldehyde (**2**) and ethylene diamine. The reaction was carried out in methanol/THF at room temperature and product was separated out after stirring of 3 h. The compound (**2**) was prepared from bromo-aldehyde (**1**) using nucleophilic substitution reaction with *N*-methylimidazole in dry acetonitrile. After 10 h of refluxing the product (**2**) was separated out as crystalline solid. The products were characterized using CHN-analysis.

Binding study of compound N1 with cations :

To find out the binding behavior of receptor **N1**, solution of receptor was prepared in H₂O : methanol (80 : 20) at concentration of 5 μM (pH = 7.5, HEPES buffer). To this stock solution various metal ions (Ni²⁺, Ag⁺, Ca²⁺, Cu²⁺, Pb²⁺, K⁺, Sr²⁺, Hg²⁺, Fe²⁺, Cd²⁺, Cr²⁺, Mn²⁺, Co²⁺, Hg²⁺ and Na⁺) were added at concentration of 7.5 μM and to maintain uniformity, the solution was sonicated for 10 min. UV-Visible absorption spectra of complex show two absorption maxima at 260 nm and 322 nm (Fig. S1), that are corresponds toward *n* to π* and π to π* transition respectively. Emission spectra of receptor were recorded on excitation wavelength 322 nm. Initially, receptor show very less emission intensity at 442 nm due to photo induced electron transfer mechanism caused by lone pair of imine linkage as well as oxygen (Fig. 1A). It was observed that fluorescence intensity was increased with interaction of Hg^{II}, Ag^I and Pb^{II} significantly whereas other metal ions did not show any significant change in emission profile. This large enhancement in emission profile attributes towards the cancellation of PET mechanism. Now to confirm the binding, fluorescence intensity was recorded at 442 nm and graph was plotted between concentration of three metal ions Hg^{II}, Ag^I and Pb^{II} and emission intensity at 442 nm (Fig. 1B). Detection limit of receptor **N1** was calculated from calibration curve using 3-sigma method which was found to be 7 nM, 15 nM and 36 nM respectively for Hg^{II}, Pb^{II} and Ag^I.

$$DL = \frac{3 \times S.D.}{m}$$

Here S.D. is the standard deviation of blank signal and *m* is the slope of calibration curve.

Effect of pH and salt strength :

To analyses the working pH conditions for receptor **N1**, fluorescence intensity of receptor was recorded at different pH conditions. It was observed that compound **N1** show negligible fluorescence from pH range 5 to 10 (Fig. 2). Although technically at lower pH, receptor should be protonated and photo induced electron transfer mecha-

Fig. 1. (A) Changes in emission spectra upon addition of 1.5 equivalents of different metal ions to a 5 μM solution of receptor **N1** in water/methanol (80 : 20, HEPES 10 mM, pH = 7.4) excited at $\lambda_{ex} = 322$ nm. (B) Linear relationship between Hg^{II}, Pb^{II}, Ag^I concentration and fluorescence intensity at 442 nm with excitation at $\lambda_{ex} = 322$ nm (left Y-axis). (C) Comparison of the fluorescence intensity of receptor **N1** (5 μM) at 442 nm in presence of different metal ion in water/methanol (80 : 20, HEPES 10 mM, pH = 7.4) with excitation at $\lambda_{ex} = 322$ nm.

nism should be OFF. However emission intensity of receptor remains below 50, that might be due reversibility of Schiff base bond at acidic pH³⁷⁻³⁹. Similarly emission intensity at 442 nm was recorded in presence of Hg²⁺ (7.5 μM). Large enhancement in emission intensity of **N1** upon addition of Hg²⁺ at basic as well as acidic pH, indicated that sensor is capable to detect these metal ions in pH range from 4.5 to 10. Similarly to check the effect of ionic strength of solution on the binding affinity of receptor, the fluorescence intensity at 442 nm was re-

corded at different concentration of tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate. It was observed that emission intensity was remaining same upto 100 mM addition of perchlorate ion, which inveterate that sensor is capable to detect the cations not only diverse range of pH but also at high concentration of ionic species. Therefore the receptor can be applicable for detection of analytes in real samples as well.

Binding constant and stoichiometry of complex :

Binding constant of receptor **N1** with three metal ions

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on fluorescence intensity of **N1** in absence and presence of Hg^{2+} .

was calculated using by Benesi-Hildebrand plot. A curve was plotted between inverse of concentration of metal ions and inverse of change in emission intensity at 442 nm. Using linear fitting, intercept and slope was calculated and binding constant was determined by dividing intercept with slope (Fig. 3A). Among these metal ions, Hg^{2+} has largest value of binding constant. Order of binding behavior of receptor **N1** with metal ions is given below

Similarly, to calculate the stoichiometry of complex, Job's

plot has been constructed (Fig. 3B). A curve was plotted between mole fraction of **N1** receptor and $[\text{HG}]$, here $[\text{HG}]$ is the concentration of complex **N1** with metal ions. This curve show maximum value of $[\text{HG}]$ at mole fraction of 0.5, which pronounce that stoichiometry of complex is 1 : 1. In other words one molecule of receptor is required form encapsulation of one cation.

Response time :

To calculate response time of receptor **N1** toward Hg^{2+} ion, fluorescence intensity of receptor **N1** at 442 nm was recorded at three different concentration of Hg^{2+} . The response of receptor was observed in a short span of time (Fig. 4). It was observed that fluorescence intensity increases up to five minutes after that it become stable which suggest that receptor take five minutes to completely bind with metal ion. Therefore all fluorescence spectra were recorded after five minutes of mixing.

Possible mechanism :

As describe above among the tested metal ions Hg^{2+} , Ag^+ and Pb^{2+} are showing large enhancement in emission profile. It means only these cations bind with **N1** selectively. The reason of selectivity can be explained on the basis of various factors. The interaction of above cations with bromide is well known. Therefore it is purposed that initially bromide ion bind with metal ions which will carry cations to the cavity formed by dipodal Schiff base receptor. Another metal ion has less affinity for

Fig. 3. (A) Plot of $1/[\text{Hg}^{2+}]$ vs $1/(F - F_0)$ for determination of binding constant. (B) Job's plot with a 1 : 1 stoichiometry.

Fig. 4. Response time of receptor **N1** toward Hg²⁺ in H₂O/methanol (8 : 2, v/v, 10 mM HEPES buffer, pH = 7.4) : change in fluorescence intensity at 442 nm with respect to time.

Fig. 5. Possible mechanism for increase in fluorescence intensity.

bromide ion and hence does not show significant change in emission intensity. Here bromide ions only act as carrier, which carry metal ions inside the cavity formed by dipodal ligand which is the actual signaling unit (Fig. 5).

Real sample analysis : To evaluate the practical application of prepared receptor, sample of water was collected from river and tap and 5 μM solution of **N1** was prepared. A known concentration of Hg²⁺ was spiked into the samples and emission intensity at 442 nm was recorded. The obtained emission intensity was correlated with calibration curve to obtain the concentration of metal ions. Also to validate the analysis concentration of metal ions also calculated using ion chromatography, which was perfectly matched with results, obtained using fluorescence methods (Table 1).

Table 1. Result of Hg^{II} and bromide sensing in real samples

Sample	Hg ^{II} added (mM)	Hg ^{II} found (mM)		Recovery (%)
		Present method	IC	
River water				
1	0	-	-	
2	2	1.97	1.98	98.5
3	4	3.89	3.95	97.3
Tap water				
1'	0	-	-	
2'	2	1.94	1.96	97.0
3'	4	3.91	3.94	97.8

Conclusion

The receptor **N1** was developed for determination of Hg^{II}, Ag^I and Pb^{II} ion in aqueous medium. There are

various factors which provide selectivity for these metal ions such as affinity of these metals for bromide ion as well as imine linkage. The receptor **N1** show excellent binding with above metal ions and the binding constant were calculated using Benesi-Hildebrand method. Among these Hg²⁺ ion shows highest affinity for **N1**. The results obtained using receptor **N1** also validated by measuring concentrations of these ions with ion channel chromatography.

General : All chemicals were purchased from Aldrich Chemical Co. and were used as-received without further purification. CHN analysis was performed using a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHN Elemental Analyzer, while pH measurements were carried out with a ME/962P instrument. Absorption spectra were recorded using UV-Vis absorp-

Scheme 1. Synthesis scheme of receptor **3**.

tion spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-2400). A Perkin-Elmer L55 fluorescence spectrophotometer equipped with quartz cuvettes (path length = 1 cm) was employed for fluorescence measurements, with a xenon lamp as the excitation source. The concentrations of heavy metal ions also determined using ion chromatography (930 Compact IC Flex, metrohm).

Cation binding studies :

Binding studies with receptor **N1** were carried out using fluorescence spectroscopy in an aqueous medium at room temperature. To induce the uniformity, the solutions were sonicated for an adequate time before recording the spectra. UV-Vis absorption spectra of receptor **N1** exhibited a maximum absorption peak at 322 nm. Upon excitation at 322 nm, receptor **N1** was showing weak emission around 442 nm. For cation binding studies, a 5 μM solution of receptor **N1** was prepared in water/methanol (80 : 20). The pH of all solutions was maintained at 7.4 using HEPES buffer. Fluorescence spectra were recorded upon addition of 1.5 equiv. (7.5 mM) of metal ions.

Synthesis of compound 2 : The compound **2** was synthesized using our previously reported method³³. A solution of compound **1** (4.52 g, 20 mmol) and *N*-methyl imidazole (1.68 g, 20 mmol) in CH_3CN (40 mL) was heated to reflux for 10 h under argon. After completion of the reaction, the solvent was evaporated using a rotary evaporator. The product was recrystallized from EtOH to yield compound **2** (6.01 g, 96%). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{15}\text{BrN}_2\text{O}_2$: C, 50.18; H, 4.86; N, 9.00. Found : C 50.11; H, 4.80; N, 8.91.

Synthesis of compound N1 : Compound **1** and **2** were synthesized using our previous reported method³³. For

the synthesis of compound **N1**, in a round bottom flask 304 mg of compound **2** was dissolved in methanol/tetrahydrofuran and 60 mg of ethylene diamine was added to the solution. The product was separated out after 3 hours of stirring at room temperature. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{34}\text{Br}_2\text{N}_6\text{O}_2$: C, 52.03; H, 5.30; N, 13.00. Found : C, 51.96; H, 5.24; N, 12.94.

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